

Assessment of Vegetation Cover and Water Volume of Awba Dam Catchment Area of University of Ibadan using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

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Abstract

Catchment areas play critical role in water regulation, soil conservation, and ecosystem health. Yet, the Awba Dam Catchment Basin (ADCB) at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria, lacks detailed information on its delineation, land use land cover (LULC), and water volume dynamics, which hinders sustainable management. Therefore, this study was designed to investigate vegetation cover and water volume dynamics in ADCB using imageries from Da-Jiang Innovations (DJI) Phantom 4 drone over a period one-year (February 2022 to February 2023) at three-month intervals. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) imagery was processed using Agisoft Metashape to generate dense point clouds, meshes, Digital Elevation Models (DEM) to produce orthomosaic images. The orthomosaic images were classified into LULC using Maximum Likelihood Algorithm, while water volume was determined using area and volume statistics module algorithm. Three LULC were identified: bare land, vegetation, and water body. Results revealed that significant fluctuations in vegetation and bare land were driven by agricultural activities, from 40.0% and 6.5%, respectively in February 2022 to 71.2% and 39.4%, respectively in February 2023. Water body was lowest (13.4%) in February 2022 and highest (24.1%) in May 2022, while water volume fluctuated from 0.92 GL to 5.04 GL, reflecting seasonal and management influences. Accuracy assessments demonstrated high reliability, with kappa statistics ranging from 80% to 100%. This study underscores the importance of active management practices in shaping land cover changes and highlights the potential of UAV technology for efficient data collection and monitoring in catchment areas. The findings provide valuable insights for sustainable water resource management and ecosystem conservation in the ADCB and similar regions.

Keywords: Catchment Basin, UAV, Land use Land cover, and Orthomosaic.

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INTRODUCTION

Catchment areas are locations in low-lying terrain where water from higher areas move into a single water body like lake or Dam. Trees are vital to catchment areas, as they provide a range of important ecological services, like water regulation, soil conservation, biodiversity conservation, carbon sequestration, among others (Onaindia et al., 2013). Catchment basin plantation is the planting of trees in catchment areas to protect and conserve water (Moyo et al., 2016). Plantations for watershed and catchment

management are vital tools for improving water quality, preventing flooding, and reducing erosion, as trees absorb water, slow runoff, enhance water storage, provide shade to cool water temperatures, reduce sediment, pollutants, and contaminants in water (Basuki, 2019). Despite their importance, there is limited information on the delineation and land use land cover (LULC) dynamics of Awba Dam Catchment Area at University of Ibadan, Nigeria, which hinders effective management and conservation efforts. Accurate LULC information is essential for sustainable resource management,

especially in the face of climate change and degradation (Alegbeleye et al., 2024).

According to Chowdhury et al. (2020), the settings of the gradient from the off-take to the outfall of any particular stream, each part of the catchment is a vital element of the watershed through which water drains to its lower point along with influential nutrients, chemicals, debris, etc. There is knowledge gap in understanding the water volume dynamics of Awba Dam because of lack of research on its volume changes over time, despite observations that the dam is shrinking in size. Addressing this gap is critical because siltation and reduced storage capacity can lead to flooding, erosion, and ecological impacts, such as the decline in fish species due to inorganic fertilizer overuse. Deng et al. (2015) asserted that multiple forms of LULC could influence the hydrological characteristics of watersheds but information regarding the LULC for this catchment area is lacking.

In recent times, the use of remote sensing platforms in acquiring data has been tremendously promising because of characteristics like wide coverage, high revisit frequency, and rich information that could be acquired; with the different time-space spectral acquired from Land satellite imagery collections used in LULC mapping (Wang et al., 2020). Current advancements in remote sensing platforms, such as Sentinel-2 and Planet Labs, offer high-resolution imagery and frequent revisit capabilities, enabling detailed LULC mapping and monitoring. These tools can provide critical insights into vegetation distribution, water volume dynamics, and the impacts of siltation and land use changes in the Awba Dam catchment. Despite these technological advancements, there is a lack of documented information on the spatial distribution of vegetation, the current volume of water in dam, and the ecological impacts of these changes. This study was designed to bridge these knowledge gaps. By leveraging on

geospatial technologies to provide baseline information on LULC and water volume dynamics, this research supports sustainable environmental conservation, inform decision-making, and offers valuable data for forest managers and researchers.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study area is situated at the southern region of the University of Ibadan campus, at an elevation of about 185 m above sea level (Akin-Oriola, 2003). It is located within Latitudes 7°25'58.00"N and 7°26'42.00"N and Longitudes 3°53'21.00"E and 3°54'26.00"E. The dam was built in April 1964 by the University Community with the primary aim of providing water storage facility for domestic use, laboratory purposes, and the cultivation of tablefish (Olajuyigbe et al., 2022). The dam has been remodeled since 2011 as a tourism site, although it continues to serve as a valuable location for hydrobiological and fisheries research activities (Ojo, 2016). The Awba River flows through various parts of academic areas of the University, including the faculties of Science and Social Sciences, as well as the Department of Petroleum and Agricultural Engineering. Its path leads to the University dam/ reservoir, which is located close to the Zoological Garden of the University (Figure 1).

The University of Ibadan is situated on the northern boundary of lowland rainforest zone of southwestern Nigeria. This location falls within a transitional area that bridges the gap between the rainforest and the derived savannah zone. The climate in this region is characterized by moderate humidity and relatively dry conditions. The mean annual rainfall is about 1220 mm, with a unique double-peak pattern observed in June and August. The rainy season extends for eight months (April to October) while the dry season spans from November to March (Oyewo et al. 2021).

Figure 1: Awba Dam, University of Ibadan

Data Collection

In the ADCB of University of Ibadan, mixed-species plantations comprising indigenous tree species were established to enhance biodiversity and support conservation efforts. The plantations, currently two years old, consist of various combinations of the following species: *Terminalia superba*, *Khaya senegalensis* and *Parkia biglobosa*, *Terminalia superba*, *Khaya senegalensis*, *Khaya ivorensis* and *Parkia biglobosa*, *Triplochiton scleroxylon*, *Azelia Africana*, and *Mansonia altissima*. Weeding and beating-up operations were also carried out to reduce competitions between the weeds and tree crops.

The Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) dataset for this study was collected from February 2022 to February 2023 at three-month intervals. High-resolution imagery/ Aerial photographs were captured and collected using a Da-Jiang Innovations (DJI) Phantom 4 pro v2.0 drone with a 20-megapixel and Red Green Blue (RGB) Camera. The specification of the drone utilized is given on Table 1. The flight route plan was organized on the DJI pilot application. An altitude of 100 m, 70% side overlap, 80% frontal overlap, and 173° course angle were configured for each flight.

Table 1: Specifications of the DJI Phantom 4 Pro V2.0 UAV

	Specification Value
Camera	1-inch CMOS with effective pixel resolution of 20 MP
Gimbal	3-axis (pitch, roll, yaw)
Max flight duration	Approx. 30 minutes
Weight	1375 g
Speed	In S-mode max 20 m/s

Source: Yordanov and Mollov, (2022)

Data Analysis

Delineation of Awba Dam Catchment Basin and its land use land cover

Image Processing

Before the UAV flights, DJI Pilot software was used for UAV flight planning. The entire study area was covered from 100m flight height. The minimum overlap ratios in the front and side were 80% and 60%, respectively. This was necessary to achieve adequate overlap of feature points common to adjacent and successive images for proper alignment. Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) was ≤ 2.24 cm. At every field data collection, a total of 2,450 images were captured. The captured images were imported into the Agisoft metashape (Figure 2). After

loading the images, alignment was carried out (Figure 3). The metashape searched for feature points on the images and matches them across images into tie points. The programme also found the position of the camera for each image and refined camera calibration parameters. The results were visualized in form of a sparse point cloud and a set of camera positions (Figure 4). The next step was to generate a surface in 3D (mesh) and/or Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (Figure 5). The Polygonal model (mesh) was textured for photorealistic digital representation of the object/scene and exported in numerous formats compatible with post-processing software. The last step was creation of Orthomosaic images (Figure 6), which was georeferenced and used as a base layer for various types of maps and further post processing analysis.

Figure 2: Process of importing the UAV images in Agisoft Metashape

Figure 3: Alignment of UAV images in Agisoft Metashape

Figure 4: Development of Dense Cloud for UAV images in Agisoft Metashape

Figure 5: Development of Digital Elevation Model from Dense Cloud

Figure 6: Development of Orthomosaic images from Digital Elevation Model

Image classification

Supervised Classification

Supervised classification is a method used to assign unknown pixels to specific classes based on samples of known identity. It involves using pixels that have already been assigned to information classes as training data to classify new, unclassified pixels. One of the main benefits of supervised classification is that it provides the analyst with control over the selected information categories, allowing them to tailor the classification to their specific needs. While this control is advantageous, it can also have its drawbacks. The imposition of a classification

structure on the data by the analyst may not always accurately represent the actual classes present in the data. This means that the selected classes may not perfectly align with the true characteristics of the data being classified (Campbell, 2002). In this study, the Maximum Likelihood Classification Algorithm was employed for the supervised classification process.

The classification of the study area was carried out on the imageries in Data Management Tools using ArcMap. A modified version of the Anderson (1976) scheme of land use/land cover classification was adopted (Table 2).

Table 2: Modified version of the Anderson scheme of land use/cover classification

LULC Categories	Description
Vegetation	Cropland and Pasture, Orchards, Groves, Vineyards, Nurseries, Ornamental Horticultural Areas, Plantation and mixed forest
Bare land	Sandy areas, barely exposed rock, transitional area, and open land.
Waterbody	Streams, lakes, and reservoirs

Source: Anderson, (1976)

Change Detention Analysis

To determine the rate of changes over time in the study area, change detention examination was carried out. The percentage change for each quarter and the rate of change between the quarter were all calculated using the formula 1 below.

$$\text{Change } (\Delta) = Q_2 - Q_1 \quad (1)$$

Average rate of change (AVR) was computed using equation 2:

$$\text{AVR} = \frac{Q_2 - Q_1}{T_2 - T_1} \quad (2)$$

Percent Change Per Year (%Δ/yr.) was computed using equation 3:

$$\% \Delta / \text{yr.} = \frac{Q_2 - Q_1}{Q_1} \quad (3)$$

Where Δ represents change; Q_2 and Q_1 are the area sizes in the initial Quarter T_1 and final Quarter T_2 respectively.

Accuracy Assessment

The user's accuracy (UA), producer's accuracy (PA), overall accuracy (OA), and kappa coefficient (k) were computed to quantitatively gauge the concordance between the classified results and the data. Accuracy Assessment was computed using the following equations (4 to 7);

$$\text{UA} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Classified Pixels in each category}}{\text{Total Number of Classified Pixels in that category}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{PA} = \frac{\text{Total Number of correctly Classified Pixels}}{\text{Total Number of Reference Pixels in that category}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{OA} = \frac{\text{Total Number of correctly Classified Pixels(Diagonal)}}{\text{Total Number of Reference Pixels}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$k = \frac{(TS \times TCS) - \sum(\text{Column Total} \times \text{Row Total})}{TS^2 - \sum(\text{Column Total} \times \text{Row Total})} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Determination of Volume of Awba Dam

Vectorization

Vectorization is the process of distilling points, lines and polygons from a scanned image. The orthomosaiced processed image was used to generate accurate vector data, which visualised

the extent of the Awba Catchment Basin for the period examined in this study.

Volume Calculation

The calculation of the lake water volume was carried out using the Area and Volume Statistics module in ArcGIS Pro v3.1.1 3D Analyst. To create the physical model of the lake water body, the underwater terrain Triangular Irregular Network (TIN) and water surface were intersected. This intersection formed the basis of the physical model. The physical model was further divided into multiple triangular prisms. This was achieved by projecting each vertex of the triangles onto the water surface. By doing so, each triangular prism representing a portion of the lake's water volume was formed. To determine the total water volume, the volumes of each triangular prism were summed together. (Mi *et al.*, 2007):

$$V = \sum_{i=1}^n S_i(h_i + h_{i+1} + h_{i+2})/3 \quad (8)$$

Where: V = total volume (m^3), S_i = projection area (m^2) of the underwater terrain triangle surface on the water surface, h_i , h_{i+1} , and h_{i+2} are distance (m) of the underwater triangle vertexes to the water surface, and n is the number of triangular grids (Lai *et al.*, 2009).

RESULTS

Awba Dam Catchment Basin and its Land use land cover

Table 3 shows the Land Use Land Cover of Awba Dam Catchment Basin, which are; Vegetation, Waterbody and bareland. The Vegetation, which had the largest area coverage initially, experienced some fluctuations (Table 3; Figures 7 to 11). In February 2022, about 22.5 ha, accounting for 68.3% of the total land area were covered with vegetation (Figure 7). This decreased to 19.2 ha (58.4%) in May, 2022 (Figure 8) but rebounded in August 2022 to 23.4 ha (71.2%) (Figure 9) but decreased again in November 2022 (Figure 10) and February 2023

(Figure 11) to 15.7 ha (47.6%) and 13.1 ha (40.0%), respectively (Table 3). Water body covered 4.4 ha, accounting for 13.4% of the total area in February 2022 (Figure 7). It increased to 7.9 ha (24.1%) in May 2022 (Table 3 and Figure 8) and then reduced slightly to 7.3 ha (22.3%) in August 2022, which indicates a notable change in the landscape during the time. The reduction in water body continued slightly till November 2022 (Figure 10) and February 2023 (Figure 11), covering about 6.9 ha (20.9%) and 6.8 ha (20.6%) respectively (Table 3). Bare land showed a different pattern. It covered about 6.0 ha (18.3%) in February 2022, decreased to 5.8 ha (17.5%) in May 2022 and reached its lowest value of 2.1 ha (6.5%) in August 2022. However, it experienced a substantial increase in subsequent months, reaching 10.3 ha (31.4%) in November 2022 and 12.9 ha (39.4%) in February 2023.

The Land Cover Change

From February 2022 to May 2022, Awba Dam catchment area vegetation and bare land had negative changes with a decrease of -1.08 ha/month and -0.09 ha/month respectively. Waterbody had an increase of 1.17 ha/month (Figure 12). Following a similar trend, bare land and water body had negative changes with a decrease of -1.21 ha/month and -0.19 ha/month respectively from May 2022 to August 2022, while vegetation increased by 1.40 ha/month (Figure 13). This trend continued from August 2022 to November 2022, vegetation and water body had negative changes, with a decrease of -2.58 ha/month and -0.15 ha/month respectively while bare land increased by 2.74 ha/month (Figure 14). However, the trend changed from November 2022 to February 2023, with vegetation and water body having negative changes with a decrease of -0.84 ha/month and -0.03 ha/month, respectively while bare land increased by 0.87 ha/month (Figure 15).

Table 3: Land Use Land Cover of Awba Dam Catchment Basin

LULC Classes	February, 2022		*May, 2022		August, 2022		*November, 2022		February, 2023	
	Area (ha)	Area (%)	Area (ha)	Area (%)	Area (ha)	Area (%)	Area (ha)	Area (%)	Area (ha)	Area (%)
Waterbody	4.4	13.4	7.9	24.1	7.3	22.3	6.9	20.9	6.8	20.6
Bareland	6.0	18.3	5.8	17.5	2.1	6.5	10.3	31.4	12.9	39.4
Vegetation	22.5	68.3	19.2	58.4	23.4	71.2	15.7	47.6	13.1	40.0
Total	32.9	100.0	32.9	100.0	32.9	100.0	32.9	100.0	32.9	100.0

* Indicates when weeding took place in ADCB

Figure 7: February 2022 Land Cover Changes

Figure 8: May 2022 Land Cover Changes

Figure 9: August 2022 Land Cover Changes

Figure 10: November 2022 Land Cover Changes

Figure 11: February 2023 Land Cover Changes

Figure 12: Land cover trend between February 2022 to May 2022

Figure 13: Land cover trend between May 2022 to August 2022

Figure 14: Land cover trend between August 2022 to November 2022

Figure 15: Land cover trend between November 2022 to February 2023

Accuracy Assessment

The evaluation of accuracy for the LULC trend analysis involved measuring user's accuracy (Ua), producer's accuracy (Pa), Kappa statistics (k), and overall accuracy across the months under consideration. Table 4 indicates that the fraction accuracy for user's accuracy (Ua), and producer's accuracy (Pa) was greater than 50%.

The kappa statistics shows that the accuracies for February 2022, May 2022, August 2022, November 2022 and February 2023 were 80%, 80%, 90%, 90%, and 100% respectively. The overall accuracy for February 2022, May 2022, August 2022, November 2022 and February 2023, were 86.67%, 86.67%, 93.30%, 93.33% and 100% respectively.

Table 4: Error matrix for the Accuracy assessment

LULC	May-22		Aug-22		Nov-22		Feb-23	
	Pa	Ua	Pa	Ua	Pa	Ua	Pa	Ua
Waterbody	100	100	100	90	100	100	100	100
Bareland	87.5	70	90	90	83.3	100	100	100
Vegetation	75	90	90.91	100	100	80	100	100
Kappa statistics	80		90		90		100	
Overall accuracy	86.67%		93.30%		93.33%		100%	

Water Volume in Awba Dam

The water volume in Awba dam in February 2022 was recorded to be 0.92 GL (Table 5). There was a sudden increase in water volume in May 2022, which appeared to be a significant surge, with the volume reaching its peak of 5.04 GL. However, the volume suddenly reduced to 2.90 GL in August until it started increasing gradually from November (3.24 GL) and February (3.91 GL). Generally, the volume of water in Awba Dam Catchment Basin (ADCB) did not follow any pattern within the period under investigation. Similarly, the area of the dam

exhibited fluctuations during the study period. The area (4.4 ha) in February 2022 and increased to 7.9 ha in May of the same year. However, it reduced from August 2022 (7.2 ha) to February 2023 (6.8 ha).

The water surface level demonstrated a corresponding pattern to the water volume. The baseline water level data was 188.03 m in February 2022, which increased to 284.17 m in May 2022, reaching its highest point before it reduced to 203.73 m in August 2022. However, it started rising again from 217.52 m in November 2022 to 240.22 m in February 2023.

Table 5: Water Volume in Awba Dam

Month	Water Volume (GL)	Area of Dam (ha)	Water Surface Level (m)
February, 2022	0.92	4.4	188.03
*May, 2022	5.04	7.9	284.17
August, 2022	2.90	7.3	203.73
November, 2022	3.24	6.9	217.52
February, 2023	3.91	6.8	240.22

**indicates when the removal of Water Icing took place in ADCB*

DISCUSSION

Remote sensing has made it easy to monitor the changes in Land use and Land cover of an area in order to understand the relationship between humans and nature. The vegetation and bare land in the ADCB showed fluctuations throughout the months due to frequent planting of forest seedlings, weeding and beating-up activities within the ADCB. The weeding was very crucial at the early time of transplanting to avoid a situation whereby the forest seedlings will be choked to death due to the presence of weeds. It was very difficult to determine the

vegetal trend throughout the study period because the trees are still in the juvenile stage, which was about 2 years aside the beating-up areas. The reduction in vegetal composition in the months of May and November, 2022 was because of the weeding, while similar reduction in February, 2023 was largely because of the dry season when naturally there is reduction in greenness. The spectral reflectance of the plant at this stage is low thereby giving an impression that the vegetal cover is low. Whenever the vegetation is high within the first 6 months of the year, there was no increase in the growth of the established trees in the plots but the weed.

Until weeding is no more needed, the fluctuation in the vegetal cover of the ADCB will continue. This result is at variance with that of Oluwajuwon *et al.* (2021), who examined the forest cover dynamics of a lowland rainforest in southwestern Nigeria using GIS and Remote Sensing techniques and reported a consistent trend of deforestation. Similarly, Alo *et al.* (2022); Toyinbo *et al.* (2021); Nwatu *et al.* (2021); and Jebiwott *et al.* (2021) made similar observations in their studies. This study has investigated the spatial dynamics in water volume and land use and land cover in the study area. The study revealed an increase in bare land because of the weeding activities carried out in ADCB.

The fluctuations in water volume, area, and water surface level of Awba Dam during the study period gave important insights into the dynamics of the hydrological characteristics of the dam. These changes could be as a result of factors like: precipitation, water inflow, and water management practices in the Dam. According to Zhu *et al.* (2021), evaporation and precipitation contribute largely to changes in the water volume, surface area and level which agrees with the position of previous studies (Soboyejo, 2021; Bouchez *et al.*, 2016). These findings have significant implications for water resource management and ecosystem health. Continuous monitoring and analysis of these hydrological parameters provide valuable information for assessing water availability, estimating the dam's capacity, and implementing appropriate water conservation measures.

Adequate provisions should be made to finance the collection of data using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) within the study area. Investing in UAV technology will enable efficient and cost-effective data collection, providing valuable information on land cover changes and other relevant parameters. This financial support will ensure proper monitoring of the study area and enable timely decision-making based on accurate and up-to-date data.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study employed Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology to assess vegetation cover and

water volume dynamics in the Awba Dam Catchment Basin (ADCB) at the University of Ibadan, Nigeria. The findings revealed significant fluctuations in LULC, particularly in vegetation and bare land, driven by activities like weeding and tree planting. Water body area and volume also exhibited seasonal variations, influenced by precipitation, water inflow, and management practices. The study highlights the importance of active management practices in shaping LULC changes and underscores the potential of UAV technology for efficient and cost-effective monitoring of catchment areas. These findings offer valuable baseline data for sustainable water resource management and ecosystem conservation in the ADCB and similar regions.

To ensure sustainable management of ADCB, continuous monitoring using UAV technology should be prioritized to track long-term changes in vegetation cover, water volume, and land use. Sustainable land management practices, such as controlled weeding schedules and reforestation efforts, should be promoted to minimize soil erosion and enhance ecosystem stability. Improved water resource management, including regular assessment of precipitation patterns and measures to mitigate siltation, is essential to optimize water storage and distribution. Further research on the long-term ecological impacts of LULC changes and water volume dynamics, supported by interdisciplinary collaboration, is crucial for informed decision-making and innovation in catchment management. By implementing these measures, the ADCB can be preserved as a vital ecological and water resource for future generations.

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